

COMMON ELEMENTS OF SUFI- BHAKTI TRADITIONS

Md. Jawaid Akhtar

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Persian

Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti Urdu Arabi Farsi University, Lucknow, India

Abstract

Religion plays significant role in shaping human relationships which in turns helps in strengthening social bodings and setting up an environment of peaceful coexistence. There is no doubt that each religion of the world preaches peace and love and if interpreted in their true spirits would always help in resolving various social conflicts in the world. When we analyze the socio religious movements of India, two of them; the Sufi and the Bhakti movements, have played quite a significant role in setting up socio-religious harmony in our country. This does not mean that other movements were of any less importance, because each such movement has played its role in one way or the other. This paper is an attempt at looking at the role of Sufi- Bhakti traditions in creating social harmony in India and also to find out their commonalities.

Introduction

India has been a land of great saints and Sufis and has been assimilating in its fold various cultures and thoughts from time to time. It is the land of ancient wisdom, where Sufism and elements of Bhakti, in their true spirit has flourished from time immemorial.

The teachings of the Bhakti and Sufi saints had much in common which can be traced back from different ages in various regions, and though both movements were not of the same period, they were for some time contemporary. Though Sufi movement and traditions had been in prevalence in other parts of the world prior to eleventh century , it was introduced in India by none other than the great Sufi saint Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti. The Bhakti movement, which was highly influenced by Buddhism, was a combination of Hinduism and Buddhism, and the birth of Bhakti can be attributed to Sankaracharya melding the best of both faiths in the eighth century in south India, spreading to north India during the twelfth century after the decline of Buddhism in this area. The regions where they preached were different. Sufism was concentrated in north India, their Suhrawardy *silsila* located in Punjab, Sind and Bengal, the Chishti *silsila* in Delhi and the Doab region, and the Firdausi *silsila* centralized in Bihar. Although the Bhakti movement started in south India, it spread all over the north to different regions by different saints.

Sufis were organized into different *silsilas* or orders, based on their views and practices. There were many silsilas, such as *Suhrawardi*, *Chishti*, *Qadariya*, and *Firdausi*. Those saints who were leading figures lent a name to the *silsila*. It consisted of people who had become disciples of certain Sufis and would follow the path shown by him. A few famous Sufis of the *Chishti silsila* were Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti, Khwaja Qutubuddin Bakhtiyar Kaki, Shaikh Hamiduddin Nagori, Khwaja Fariduddin Masud, Shaikh Nazimuddin Auliya, Shaikh Nasiruddin Mahmood, Shaikh Burhanuddin Gharib. The *Chishti* were prevalent in the Ganga-Yamuna doab region. The *Suhrawardi*, famous in Punjab, Sind and Bengal, was lead by saints such as Shaikh Bahauddin Zakariya, Shaikh Jalaluddin Tabrizi. The *Firdausi* order was an off-shoot of *Suhrawardi*, famous in Bihar. Shaikh Sharfuddin Yahya Maneri was the most important Sufi belonging to this *silsila*. The Qalandari order covered most of the wandering dervishes The *Rishi* order in Kashmir was established by Shaikh Nuruddin Wali.

Similarly, the Bhakti movement has generally been divided into two phases. The first phase was eighth century onwards, started by Sankaracharya in South India. It was revived by Ramanuja in the twelfth century and spread all over north India during the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries. The most prominent Bhakti saints during this period were Namdev, Gyandev, Ramanandev, Vallabhacharya, Ektnath, Chaitanya, Kabir, Ravidas, Raidas and Nanak. These holy men belonged to the *nirguna* school. The other Bhakti school of note was the *sagunas* school, of which

Mirabai, Sahjobai, Tulsidas among others were influential during the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. Unlike the saints of the *nirguna* school, they worshipped idols in the form of Lord Rama, Krishna and others.

Socio Religious Reform Movements

The leaders of Bhakti movements who were to make a deep impact on social and religious ideas were those who were influenced by Islamic ideology, particularly Sufism and related them to ideas from the Vedas and Upanishads. (Kabir and Nanak found similarity in Islam to their ideas and related it to the formless God of Hinduism (in the Upanishads, Yogashastra). They emphasized the formless God (*nirankar*) and did not believe in idol worship. Their disciples were from both Muslim and Hindu communities. In their teachings they criticized both *ulema* and Brahmins who kept people in darkness and made them perform useless rites and rituals. The main focus of both the movements was to create an environment of social harmony through making efforts to search and find ultimate reality.

Both these movements have left a prevailing impact on religious, cultural, and social life in India. Sufi scholars traveling from all over continental Asia were instrumental in the social, economic, and philosophic development of India. Besides preaching in major cities and centers of intellectual thought, Sufis reached out to poor and marginalized rural communities and preached in local dialects such as Urdu, Sindhi, Panjabi versus Persian, Turkish, and Arabic. Sufism emerged as a "moral and comprehensive socio-religious force" that even influenced other religious traditions such as Hinduism. Their traditions of devotional practices and modest living attracted all people. Their teachings of humanity, love for God and Prophet continue to be surrounded by mystical tales and folk songs today. Sufis were firm in abstaining from religious and communal conflict and strived to be peaceful elements of civil society. Furthermore, it is the attitude of accommodation, adaptation, piety, and charisma that continues to help Sufism remain as a pillar of mystical Islam in India.

Oneness of God and Spiritual Leader - Disciple Relationship

The Sufi saints believed in oneness with God, and that union with God was the highest stage of Enlightenment, which could be achieved through love of God. To attain such a state, one was required to go through certain stages *Muqama* and the changing psychological conditions, or states (*hal*). Sufi saints asserted that for an individual to attain closeness with God, which paves the way to salvation, one should do so through service to humanity. Nizamuddin Auliya discussed this theme in one of his discourses, and retold the story of the Prophet Abraham, who would only eat in the company of guests, till one day he found himself in the presence of a single polytheist. Abraham, when he saw that he was alone with a polytheist, did not give him anything to eat. The command then came forth from God, "O Abraham, how is it that we can confer life on him [the polytheist] yet you cannot give him bread. ". This shows that Nizamuddin emphasized the presence of the Absolute Being within each human being, as every individual is the son and daughter of God, then all are equal.

As with Bhakti *gurus*, Sufis believed that closeness with God was made more possible when one had a spiritual master who could channel the 'Knowledge' and guide the individual towards the path of self surrender to God. Hence importance was given to the acquisition of a *pir* or the *guru*. From here came the *pir-mureed* and the *guru-shishya parampara* (*Guru- Chela* tradition of Bhakti). It was considered that the Sufi or Bhakti path required the strict guidance of a spiritual master, who had himself clearly understood the Knowledge and had reached the stage where he had direct communion with God. In the *pir-mureed* relation, the *mureed* or the disciple had to progress on the path of practicing self-modification (*mujaheda*), reciting and recollecting God's name, either through knowledge (*jnana*), or by concentrating on God's name (*zikr*), contemplation and meditation. In the *guru shishya-parampara*, the *shishya* had to first make himself ready to accept Knowledge. They had to be committed to be on the path of Bhakti for the rest of their life. *Guru's* word for them is the word of God. And in order to thank the *guru* for Knowledge, the

shishya is ready to do *seva* (service), *satsang* (being in company of holy men) and *bhajan* (to meditate and recite the True Name regularly). Since these saints wanted to reach the masses who were not accepted by the *ulema* and Brahmins, the Sufis and the Bhakti saints both used local dialects as a means of communication, preached in the form of couplets rather than traditional prose. The mystics of the two movements were not appreciated by the orthodox *ulema* or Brahmins, as they defied them. Most of the Sufi and Bhakti saints criticized the *ulema* and Brahmin, who kept people in darkness, and misinterpreted the religious scriptures. Both movements discarded idol worship, blind faith in scriptures, performing *namaz* without understanding the relevance of it, and discriminations of individuals in the name of gender, caste and creed. As rituals were not considered important, service to human beings had much higher spiritual significance than mere formal adherence to rituals and practices. Nizamuddin Auliya said that "Devotion to God is of two kinds: *lazmi* (obligatory) and *mutaaddi* (supererogatory). In *lazmi*, the benefit goes to the devotee alone. This type of devotion includes prayers, fasting, pilgrimage to Mecca, recitation of religious formulae, and turning over the beads of the rosary. The *mutaaddi*, by contrast, centered around other's needs, and is performed by spending money on others, showing affection to people, and generally being considerate. The reward *mutaaddi* is incalculable.

They tried to bridge the gap between the two religions (Hinduism and Islam) by teaching that God was one and the same, even if he was called by different names. Respect of fellow human beings and service to humanity was held in high esteem by both, as Sufism and Bhakti considered individuals as a temple of God.

Music was central to both movements. It was considered to imbibe a mystical state of ecstasy, when one could feel the presence of God. This music was the inner music which is constantly there till the human is 'alive'. No one plays any instrument but the music is on and when one meditates, he just needs to concentrate on it in order to reach the state of union with God. Sufi and Bhakti saints organised musical recitals (*sama* or *kirtan*) and this was a manifestation of Knowledge.

Wahdat ul-Wajud (Unity of Being)

The teachings of the Sufi saints during the Sultanate period can be traced back to the theory of *Wahdatul-Wajud* (unity of being) of Ibn al Arabi. This concept was founded on the primordial belief in the ultimate nature of unity which reduced to nothing, the ideas of the existence of entities other than God ["*A History of Sufism*" pp 103-108.] Ibn al-Arabi believed that the Absolute Being was inseparable from the Absolute Existent and was the ultimate source of Existence, that the Absolute Being had manifested Himself in every form of existence and in the highest degree in the form of Perfect Man. According to Ibn al-Arabi, the One and the many are the two aspects of one. Medieval writer, Afifi, interprets his concept and says: "*The one reveals himself in many... as an object is revealed in different mirrors, each mirror reflecting an image determined by its nature and its capacity as a recipient. Or it is like a source of light from which an infinite number of lights is derived. Or a substance which penetrates and permeates the forms of existing objects: thus, giving them their meaning and being. Or it is like a mighty sea on the surface of which we observe countless waves forever appearing and disappearing. The external drama of existence is nothing but this ever renewed creation (ai-Khalq, ai-Jadid) which is in reality a perpetual process of self revelation*". [M.M. Sharif(ed) *A History of Muslim Philosophy*, voll, p413] Ibn al-Arabi identified the Absolute with *zat* (or essence) and interpreted it as the Absolute Being (*Wujud al-Mutlaq*) calling it a source and cause of all existence.

Like Ibn al-Arabi, Sufi mystics had a deep devotion to God, and they disliked the vulgar display of wealth, degeneration of morals, and general inequality among society. The Sufi concept of *fana* [*Tarjuman ai-Ashwaq*, quoted by Afifi, "*A History of Muslim Philosophy*", vol I, p144.], or spiritual merger of the devoted with God, was central to their teachings. They emphasized *wahdad ul-wajud*, that is, Unity of Being. They believed that God is everywhere, but he is to be realized. He is in different forms of life, in all human beings and animals.

Tasawwuf, or mysticism, strove to achieve the inner realization of Divine unity by arousing the intuitive and spiritual faculties. Sufis plunged into contemplation and meditation, and adherence to a life of temperance which was an essential attribute for attaining a strong union with God.

Gnana (Intuitive Knowledge) and Guru-Shishya (Peer-Mureed) Tradition

In almost all religious scripture the universality of the Supreme Being is discussed. Hindu scriptures -the Vedas, the Upanishads, the Puranas, or the religious texts like Bhagvata Gita describe the Absolute Being as the creator, nourisher and the destroyer. The texts explain the importance of *jnana* (intuitive Knowledge) which can be taken by the individual who can then bring himself closer to God by reciting the name of God provided by *jnana*. This requires a lot of practice (*sadhana*), which is made possible through *yoga*. Yoga means union, union with the Ultimate, and this has been idealized and practiced from the beginning. It describes those who propose different beliefs about the Ultimate and those who advocate different methods of achieving the Union. The view called '*advaita*' (non-dualistic), *Vedanta* (culmination of the Vedas) best exemplifies the ideal of perfect *yoga*, which it explains [*Yoga- Union with the Ultimate*", Archie J. Bahn, Fredric Ungar Publishing Company, 1978.]

Yoga can be performed in different ways. *Karma yoga* is one form which presupposes the 'law of Karma'. *Gnana yoga* is a second way to progress towards the Union with Ultimate reality and emphasizes the attainment of understanding i.e. Path of knowledge under the supervision of a sagacious teacher (i.e. *guru*). Knowledge involves a distinction between knower and known, but in yogic intuition knower and known are one, not two. [*Yoga- Union with the Ultimate*", Archie J. Bahn, Fredric Ungar Publishing Company, 1978]. *Bhakti yoga* places importance on devotion. What one loves, that he serves. The more fully he loves it, the more completely he devotes himself to it. The greater the value of that which one loves, the more he seeks to unite himself with it, and thereby finding his own value realized in the Beloved. Such Union is complete when between lover and Beloved, and there is no difference other than *identity*.⁵⁵ Amir Khusrau, a disciple of Nizamuddin Auliya says:

"Man to shudam, tu man shudee I become you and you into me

Man tan shudam tujan shudee I become a body and you a soul

Takas na bayad baad az een So that no one can say

Man degaram tu digaree" I am one and you are other.

This is the love between God and the individual soul.

Raja yoga focuses the attention and efforts towards the body and mind for the purpose of controlling and illuminating every physical and mental element which prevents the soul from enjoying the perfect Union. *Tantric yoga* is a form of *Bhakti yoga* in which orgasm constitutes the concrete symbol of cosmic self-realisation. The goal of *Tantric yoga* is a kind of eternal orgasm.

Similarly in Buddhism and Jainism, Buddha and Mahavira explained the importance of self-realisation. They preached a middle-path which was good for humans staying in *Grihastya Ashram*. They also emphasized the knowledge which could be attained from the real *Guru*. *Guru* who was of that time and was living. That *guru* is called *Satguru* (the true living *Guru* of the period). *Bhakti* saints and disciples have much praise for these *gurus*. As Kabir said that is all this earth was paper, the water in the ocean were the ink, all the trees in the forests are to be used as pen and one would write the description of *Guru* on it, still he would not describe the *guru* wholly. Kabir says, "*Sab Dharti Kagad Karoon, Lekhani Sab Vanrai, Sab nadi Syahi Karoon, Guru Cun/ikha naa jaaye*".

Bhakti saints were monotheists who argued that salvation was granted by the grace of God if Knowledge was imparted to the individual through a living *Guru*. Most of them linked the *Bhakti Marga* with that of traditions of the Vedas. They used the scriptures to explain the theoretical aspects of Knowledge. All Bhakti saints placed emphasis on *Ek Brahma* who was the Creator and resided within the heart of each human being. For Nanak, God was one and He was the truth, the Creator, without fear and without hate, he was beyond time, immortal, and it was His spirit which pervades the universe, He is never born, He never dies, He is self-existent. For Nanak, God was formless and idols made for God were just to remember and respect the form which was read in scriptures. The formless God was worshipped since the time when humanity had threats from nature. But it is understood that the need for the Union with that power was always felt by humanity. Though at times they did not understand it and tried to fulfill their hearts with worldly things, which only served to worsen their condition.

There is a common theme that runs through the *Quran*, *Adi Granth* and the *Hindu scriptures*. Nanak called God as *Sat Kartar*, who was the True Creator or *Satnam*, whose name was the True Name. Nanak also called God as *Nirankar* and therefore he is beyond description. He says that therefore one should admit that he is beyond his imagination, and he defies description or definition, and cannot be realized from this eye or mind.

Sufi Muinuddin Chishti says:

Ek Mandir men das darwazah There is a temple with ten doors

Jamen basen kartaar that is where the god resides,

Apne-apne niyam dharma se With their own way

Puje shakal sansar! The universe worships him!

Even Kabir says the pilgrimage was in the heart of the human where God resides. Kabir says '*Naa mandir mein naa Masjid me na kabah Kailash mein, Khoji hovey to meinmil jaoun pal bhar ki talaash mein*'. There is an interesting event with Nanak that when he was resting in a mosque with his feet towards Kabah, a mullah came to say his prayer and shook Nanak rudely and said ; "*O servant of God, thou has thy feet towards Kabah, the house of god; why hast thou done such a thing?*" Nanak replied; "*Then turn my feet towards some direction where there is no God, no Kabah.*"

To realize such a God, *nam* or True Knowledge is important. This *nam* leads to union with God as we discussed earlier from *jnana* yoga in the ancient period yogis used to realize the union with God. The monotheist saints, particularly Kabir and Nanak, emphasized *satguru*. Even the Sufis stressed the importance of *pir-o-murshid* to realize the Absolute Being. Here we see that these Bhakti saints might have been influenced by Sufi traditions. One of the important agendas of both the Bhakti *Guru* and Sufi was to illuminate people regarding the limitations and restrictions of the *ulema* and Brahmin philosophies. Nanak and Kabir wrote many couplets to make people understand the importance of *Guru*. Nanak said that *Guru* is the vessel who could save the individual soul from the ocean of the world, and provide release from the cycle of life and death. "How shall! scale the fortress without a ladder? By meditating on God through the *Guru* I shall behold him. The *Guru* giving me God's name is my ladder, my boat, my raft; The *Guru* is the lake, the sea and the boat; the *Guru* is the sacred stream". Kabir said that those individuals who believe in Knowledge and Truth within themselves are to be respected as they have acknowledged the *sat guru* and have chosen to walk down the path shown by Him. "*Mahima Badi Jo Sadh Ki, Jake Nam Aadhar-- Satguru keru dayate utere bhavajal paar*". *Guru* has been revered by all the saints as Guru Arjun says that when *guru* is there, the superstitious mind of human is illuminated and he cuts the chains and frees the soul. But it can be ascertained that under the *Guru's* instruction; by meeting the True One, happiness is obtained. If the *satguru* be met, true love shall not sunder and the wealth of Divine Knowledge of the three words shall be obtained. If anyone acquires virtue, he will not forget the Pure Name. The birds which peck one, sea and land have played and gone away.

The importance of *Guru* is so much that Kabir says that if God and *Guru* both come and stand in front of one who has knowledge, that disciple should bow at *Guru* first because he is the one who made him see God who was residing within but he was ignorant of Him.

Bhakti and Sufi saints gave importance to salvation and for this Kabir emphasized the Bhakti *marga* which was based on contemplation and meditation. He stressed that at least some time in a day should be spent by the disciple reciting the name of God which is provided by *Guru* through True Knowledge. Even Nanak said this *margaas nam marga* and laid emphasis on *nam japo* as explained earlier.

All Bhakti and Sufi saints laid emphasis on *Guru-shishya parampara* (*pir-mureed* traditions). The disciples were urged to follow the sayings of the *Guru* if they desired the eternal love of God. For this they had to shed their ego as the presence of ego obstructed the realization of Knowledge and love of God. He had to surrender himself fully to his *Guru* and should be ready to devote anything and everything in his life at the feet of *Guru*. It is considered that if someone is in love with the other person, he or she does something for the loved one. Similarly, in order to show love towards *Guru*, the disciple should be ready to do something which would please his master. *Satsang* and *Simran* were important for the disciple to fully understand Knowledge. *Satsang* is a society of holy men where description from heart is given and whatever is said by the holy man or master is not intellectualized or based on scriptures. It is purely on the basis of personal experience that holy men talk about the Absolute Being in all human beings. Very few people are lucky to be party to such society and discourse. *Satsang* is said to be a kind of 'soap' which keeps on washing the dirt and dust of *maya* (illusion) covering the human conscience even after receiving True Knowledge. It is important to listen to *satsang* for a disciple to reach the ultimate goal. For him, *seva*, *satsang* and *bhajan* (*nam jap*) are the only roads which can bring him in union with God. Kabir emphasized that life seems pointless if one is on this earth but does not take Knowledge and perform the task of a true disciple. Otherwise he is similar to an animal and cannot reform himself and release from cycle of life and death. He said that the human body is the gate to salvation, and one should develop all dimensions of their being, which includes not only their minds but their souls. After taking Knowledge, salvation can be attained but one should be involved in *seva*, *satsang* and *bhajan* in spite of staying in *grihastya ashram*. If this is not done, then that human will be crushed in the grindstone, as wheat is done and flour is made out of it. It is said that the three pillars, *seva*, *satsang* and *bhajan* act like the mast in the grindstone where if any wheat grain is left near the mast, then until the end, it will remain the same.

Bhajan/Sama, Satsang/Khanqah, Seva and Universal Brotherhood

Bhajan, *satsang* and *seva* are, as explained earlier, the three pillars of a successful life of a saint, which results in being in Union with God. Fourth and the most important pillar being the '*guru*' whose importance has been explained earlier. Sufi saints define it as *fana* where as Bhakti saints call it *yoga* or *parmatma se Milan*. Then what is *bhajan* for Sufis? One need no explanation about *qawwali* and its importance in the Sufi parlance. *Sama* is the very important in Sufi gatherings of which *qawwali* is crucial. *Bhajan* and *sama* are so similar in approach that at times it is hard to distinguish between them.

Take the example of *satsang*. These are different names for the same concept. Otherwise we would not have one of the most important apolitical sources for the study of socio-cultural history of the Sultanate period. Through the pages of *malfuzaat* one can have the feeling of *satsang*. It is a compound word made of *sat*(truth) and *sang* (gathering), i.e the gathering of the Truth, conversing with Truth. That is what exactly happened in the Sufi's *Khanqahs*. Nizamuddin Auliya stressed the importance of *satsang*. In fact his visionary personality took him a step further. The gathering at the *Khanqahs* of these saints was in fact *satsang* in the true sense and spirit of the word.

Seva, the service of God through serving humanity is the focus point of the Sufi movement. Answering to a question of his disciple, Muinuddin Chishti said that the most superior kind of worship is to assist the helpless and to feed the hungry. Nizamuddin compare 'rituals' with spices and 'service' as meat is the main ingredient of the soup. For Sufis service of humankind is the *raison d'être* of religion.

Bhakti and Sufi saints emphasized that worldly life is *maya*, and its glamour is perishable as is the human body, and it will again go back to dust. It is said that the life of a living being is like a dream, maybe of 60 years, 70 years or more, and the day the human dies, the dream breaks, and he realizes that he has lost the time in running behind *maya* and did not perform the task for which he was given this beautiful human body. Bhakti doctrine explains that the human body is the most elusive form given when the Lord showers His love to get *moksha* (salvation). Sufis and Bhakti saints said that human body had 10 gates. The body has nine natural gates or orifices; it is therefore through the tenth gate that the Divine light enters the body.

Bhakti and Sufi saints all upheld the notion that God resided within each individual and not in temples or mosques. Merely practicing a religion, reading sacred texts and performing rites and rituals, does not necessarily lead to union with God. In fact, often these external elements alienate the individual from looking within to find Knowledge and Truth. True religion is not to show off what you wear and how you keep yourself. As Nanak writes:

*Religion lieth not in visiting tombs
Nor in visiting places where they burn the dead
Not in sitting entranced in contemplation
Nor in wandering in the countryside or foreign lands
Nor in bathing at places of pilgrimage.
If thou must the path of true religion see,
Among the world's impurities, be of impurities free.
When a man meets the true guru
His doubts are dispelled
And his mind ceases its wanderings;
Drops of nectar pour down on him like rain.
His ears catch strains of sahaja's celestial music
And his mind is lit up with knowledge divine.
If thou must the path of true religion see,
Among the world's impurities, be of impurities free.
Sayeth Nanak, if thou must be a real yogi*

From eleventh century onwards in India, the contact and philosophical conflicts between the Sufis and Yogis became more frequent when Sufis came to India. The Yogis variously regarded as *Siddhas*, had close links with all the eminent Chishti saints as can be attested from their frequent visits to Nizamuddin Auliya and their heated discussions with Baba Farid and *Jamaat khana*. This practice of uninhibited interaction owes its genesis to the historical tradition preceding the establishment of Chishti *silsila* in the sub-continent throughout Turkey, Syria and Egypt. These Yogis were disciples of Goraknath, who were known as Nath Panthis. Nasiruddin Chiragh-i-Delhi was even influenced by the yogic practices of these people, and emphasized to his followers the importance of yoga as a way to help attain salvation. He stressed the importance of each breath. The yogis also had involved discussions with Nanak where he argued with them about the importance of *nam margand nam simran*. Nanak emphasized *sahaja avastha* as the state of equipoise from which the God who is purest of pure can be obtained and not by practicing asceticism. This state of equipoise is known to Sufis *asfana-ma-al-baqa*, also the *turiya avastha* of the Hindu scriptures.

At this position, the Sufi and Bhakti saints opposed their respective orthodox counterparts who tightly controlled scriptures which were meant to be disseminated to everyone. Brahmins did not allow low caste people to learn Sanskrit as it was considered to be the language of *devas*. They made these texts so complex and difficult that they

were inaccessible to the common people and their positions of power could be maintained. Though the *ulema* did not put restrictions on the study of religious texts like the Quran and Hadith, we know from historical texts that those Indians who were of low-caste and who were attracted to the Islamic philosophy of egalitarianism, became the victims of the *ulema*'s most unegalitarian practice. As discussed earlier Nizamuddin Auliya describes the importance of equality among men and women, a subject which was stressed in both religious movements. Nanak also said that one should not denigrate women as they are conceived and born as men are conceived and born. In contrast to the orthodox sections of both religions, the Bhakti and Sufi saints practiced and preached humanitarian principles of both religions, and as discussed in chapter two, it is because of this fact that they adopted the languages of the masses, hence the evolution of several local dialects. It is in the same period that Amir Khusrau started composing poems in two languages. He would write the first line in Persian and second in Hindawi. Similarly in the western part of India, Bhakti saints such as Eknath and Namdev were questioning the use of the "Holy" language of Sanskrit. They said "if Sanskrit was made by God, then who made Prakrit?".

During the thirteenth century the mystics laid importance on the indigenous dialects. The Sufis used Hindawi as the vehicle for communicating their discourses. Hindu mystical songs were recited at the *sama* gatherings. Syed Gisu Daraz admitted that each indigenous language had its own characteristics and importance, and through Hindawi the esoteric ideas of Sufism could easily be expressed.

These gatherings were common among the Sufis and Bhakti saints. In *Sarna* and *kirtan* the mystical songs were recited which brought the spiritual followers to a state of ecstasy, whereby through the music they would be in union with the Divine Being. Hindu mystical songs were also recited in the *sama* gatherings. Many talented musicians participating in the *sama* gatherings were newly converted Muslims. Shaikh Ahmed from Naharwala in Gujarat, who gave the expert renditions on Hindawi *ragas*, lived during the thirteenth century. He undoubtedly attended the most significant *sama* performance, which is clear from his presence when a Persian verse produced such powerful ecstasy in Shaikh Qutbuddin Bakhtiyar Kaki, that he died a few days later. Ahmed was said to have been a disciple of Faqir Madhu, the Imam of the Zami Mosque in Ajmer, who retained his Hindu name even after conversion. In *sama*, a *qawwal* sings poetry on musical tunes. This is also to invoke the audience to go into a trance to experience what is called the 'meeting with the Beloved'. They talk about *ishqe-i-haqeeqi* which has been explained by Bhakti saints like Kabir and Nanak, their couplets regarding this can be read in the Adi Granth. One should enjoy the worldly love which Sufis called *ishqe-i-majazazi*. This meant that when a person loved his Beloved intensely, at some point of time, a stage was attained which helped in sublimation to the spiritual love of *ishqe-i-haqeeqi*.

Similarly, Chaitanya, who introduced *kirtan*, a musical gathering in which people from a particular area assembled with all kinds of local instruments to invoke spiritual ecstasy. Musical tunes were accompanied by vocals. One member would utter sayings, which would be repeated by others in a typical style. The whole ceremony would go on throughout the night in which they were intoxicated by the ambience or chorus of the music. This invokes them to realize God within. It is possible that *kirtan* was inspired by *sama*. Kabir composed a large number of "love" songs regarding spiritual love. Chaitanya similarly described the love of Radha for Krishna and this he symbolized as meaning everyone can be the beloved of the Supreme Being. Most of the saints, like Kabir, have shown the soul as the female part in this love as it was considered that the love of female is more intense than the male. Kabir says the attraction between *jivathama* and *paramathma* (a masculine element, from *Param Purusha*) towards each other is for the ultimate union. In contrast, the Sufi's *jivathama* (human soul) which should be a prime mover in this game of love between the two, is to be taken as a masculine element as they hold the view that the love of man for the woman is always stronger and more eloquent than that of woman for man.

Relevance in Present Time

Sufi-Bhakti traditions have been relevant in all times. Even today in sama gatherings, though not as common as they were during the sultanate period, *qawwali* is still famous for bringing followers to the state of ecstasy. Shankar and Shambhu were the official *qawwals* at the *dargah* of Khwaja Gharib Nawaz of Ajmer. It is worth noting that even though Muslim, Bismillah Khan, played *shahnai* at the Vishvanath temple at Varanasi. This is not sheer coincidence, but is possibly a result of the interplay between the Bhakti and Sufi movements back in the sultanate period.

The *khanqah* of Nizamuddin was always visited by Bhakti saints, and common Hindu people, and even today, Hindus are welcome at Sufi *dargahs* all over the country. Needless to say these Hindu visitors have inherent Bhakti traits, and orthodox believers do not patronize these *dargahs*.

Bhakti saints like Kabir and Nanak can be seen in synchronization with the two spiritual movements. The Hindu saints adopted some Islamic traditions and understandings to preach their doctrines. It is evident that both the Bhakti and Sufi saints preached the same message, based on similar principles. They did not find any difference in the Absolute Being, who was the Creator, and that each individual should try to be in Union with Him. There was no clear distinction between a "Hindu" and a "Muslim" God.

The origin of the Bhakti movement can be traced back to the ancient scriptures like the Vedas, Upanishads, and Buddhist texts and was living in parallel with the Hindu, Buddhist and Jain religions. History gives importance to Hinduism as one of the oldest world religions, because of these written records, and it is from these records that we understand the importance of 'Union with God' came from such a time when humanity was born. This can be seen through one of the early religious texts, the Bhagvat Gita, which talks about Knowledge, Action and Bhakti. This is the basis of the Bhakti movement, *jnan*, or Knowledge, which has been present since time immemorial, and is still present and will remain so whilst humanity resides in this world.

Hence it can clearly be said that the core of the Sufi believe system is astoundingly similar to Bhakti. It lies in the acknowledgement of the establishment of the primordial covenant between God and the souls of men and women in a time before creation of the cosmos. The union between God and the souls of every human is known in Sufi literature as the "Day of Alast". The goal of every Muslim mystic (Sufi) thus came to recapture this experience of loving and ecstatic intimacy with the Lord of the world.

In spite of such sincere religious movements which worked to bind both communities, today people in India and the world are fighting in the name of religion. Perhaps it is because we fail to understand the importance of each human being and each breath we take. We should use the wisdom of the Bhakti and Sufi teachings and apply them to our contemporary problems.

It is in this backdrop that there is a need to study and research on various aspects of Sufi-Bhakti philosophy and literature. Their principle of simple living, promotion of the message of love and peace, emphasis on moral values and respect for all religion caste and creed along with the message of universal brotherhood has significance throughout ages and in today's world there is a great need of understanding and propagating these ideas and ideals.

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